

METHODS OF MODERN AND INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO FORMING COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

Khurramova Gulnoza Sharofiddin qizi

Master's student of the Termez State Pedagogical Institute
Theory and methodology of education (primary education)

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on communication problems that are common among elementary school students and how to solve them. At the same time, the opinions of researchers on this issue are emphasized, and at the end of the article, opinions and comments about the specific aspects of studying this issue are given.

Today, the changes implemented in the field of education system require teachers to constantly improve, enrich and develop themselves during their professional activities. Of course, every teacher is required to be active in the life of the society in accordance with the requirements of the time, therefore, the education of the modern school, which educates the student at the highest level, has a place in life, and is considered a place of education it is permissible to apply innovative approaches to the learning process.

It is somewhat inappropriate to consider the concept of innovation in the field of education as a new concept. Studying this problem, many well-known scientists - Comensky, Steiner made significant contributions to the field of pedagogy. Vygotsky discovered various fields of psychology and pedagogy. The innovative potential of pedagogical innovations is very deep, as a result of which each teacher has the opportunity to find his own methodology, which meets his personal qualities, which contributes to solving the problems of creativity, humanization, differentiation, activity and thinking is given.

The most important task of a modern school is to form a person who develops himself, that is, a person who is ready and capable of learning. Here we are referring to M. Montaigne's opinion about modern, aspiring, enthusiastic, and at the same time gifted children: "A well-organized brain is more valuable than a well-filled brain."¹

¹ Visitova LS Innovative methods of teaching in primary school // Education and training. - 2016. - No. 1. - P. 16-19.

According to recent studies, more and more changes are taking place in the primary education system, which serves as a basis for the formation of the student's personality and the development of his spiritual and intellectual potential. A primary school teacher is entrusted with many complex tasks, one of which is to create a comfortable and necessary environment for the teacher and the student, while at the same time solidly mastering knowledge, skills and abilities.

The introduction of innovative approaches in the activity of a primary school teacher is important, the basis of which is learning through activity, which is the most important component of the modern educational process. The use of innovative approaches shows that the teacher ceases to be the translator of knowledge, the only source of information: it is important for the teacher to form the ability of the student to independently obtain information and check its reliability.

An innovative approach is an approach to teaching or educational organization, the essence of which is the use of pedagogical innovations.

" pedagogical innovation " does not have a universally accepted definition. For example, this concept includes:

- targeted changes that introduce innovations into the educational environment , help to improve the characteristics of individual parts, components, and the educational system as a whole;

- the process of mastering innovations (new techniques, tools, technologies, programs, etc.);

- new methods and programs, applying them to the educational process and creative rethinking.

Pedagogical innovations are based on two main approaches:

1) student -oriented approach, the essence of which is to direct the educational process to the personality of each child. Based on this approach, the teacher takes into account the unique experience and character of each student , organizes the development of his personality and talent;

2) competence-based approach, which is considered new for the primary class. Its essence is that if it is directed to the learning result, the result is not a sum of knowledge, but a sum of skills, the student 's ability to solve problems and conflicts in different situations .²

English writer Richard Aldington said: "Nothing important to know can be taught - all a teacher can do is show the way." Currently, the school is the most important factor of personal development , it should become an effective and promising factor of the development of the society, it is necessary to constantly develop the educational system and the school. School development is done through innovation.

AI Kochetov gives the following definitions to the concept of "innovation": a comprehensive theoretical, technological and methodological concept of renewing pedagogical activity, ensuring that it is brought to a specified level. We cannot fully agree with this definition.

² Paltov.AE Innovative educational technologies: Textbook. - Vladimir: Publishing house VIGU, 2018. - 119 p.

V. Kvash and V. Latkin, "innovation is the creation of fundamentally new activity models that go beyond the norm, bring professional activity to a radically new level of quality."³ Practice shows that any innovation goes beyond the limits of normalized activity and strives for achievement. At the same time, professors and teachers of innovative schools should look at past experience, connect their activities with existing practice.

Innovative activity is one of the aspects of modern school work in the development mode, which is considered in the form of positive qualitative changes and step-by-step activity of certain levels described. Innovative activity determines the pedagogical and psychological conditions, provides a certain degree of normative limitation, introduces acceptable standards, borrows them from other fields, etc. It provides a set of tools for development, implies a conscious change of reality. Innovative activity is characterized by processes consisting of the stages of emergence, development and implementation of innovations. "Innovative activity - notes VI Gorbunov - depends on two factors: the strength of the developing innovative process and the nature of its connection with the environment. In the context of innovative schools, on the one hand, it is the validity of the choice or development of innovations, and on the other hand, the interest of teachers, students and parents.

The leading methodologist VI Gorbunova identifies five factors that help activate the innovation process:

the creative potential of school leaders, which includes the ability to change value orientations, create a new image of personal behavior ; development of new technologies and training of innovative activities of process participants; organization of intensive interaction and communication;

developed complex projects (programs, plans), which include not only the innovation process itself, but also the parameters of the environment affected by it;

- consulting projects (programs, plans) and the process itself, which ensures the reliability of managers' actions, the possibility of creating alternatives, and timely correction. The role of this factor is great, because any innovation is always associated with risk. In the conditions of innovative schools, this is not only an economic, but also a voluntary, professional, practical and moral-psychological risk. Therefore, there is a need to search for an antipode - a guarantee, which allows to avoid negative consequences, to determine and justify the conditions for achieving certain results in the process of innovation, and the possibility of compensating actions as a result of failure;

- socio - economic environment that is a guarantee of innovative activity in terms of psychological - pedagogical, scientific-methodical and material-theoretical provision;

- speech positions of participants of the innovation process. They can be characterized as active, supportive, antagonistic and inactive. It is clear that the priority of one or the other affects the capacity of the entire innovative school, that is, the ability to create and implement

³ Skripko LE Implementation of innovative teaching methods: promising opportunities or insurmountable problems? // Quality management. - 2012. - Issue 1.

innovations, to get rid of those who have lost their role, and to spread these innovations. has a significant impact on school activities.

The teacher works in a lesson that includes one or another technology, students use and improve the skills of independent work, text work, speech activity, pair and group work. Of course, such skills are formed more among students of general education schools. However, practice shows that even a primary school teacher can effectively use these technologies. In the search for a solution to the problem, teachers use the student-oriented approach of teaching, which is implemented through the introduction of information and communication technologies, cooperative pedagogy, health care in their pedagogical activities.

What is important is how the student develops the ability to respond to changes, to be flexible, to manage emotions and to search for the right information. This innovation requires a fundamental revision of the educational system, reform of the principles of educational evaluation and organization. On the basis of these approaches, teachers and methodologists develop a set of innovative pedagogical technologies - techniques, methods and methods of knowledge transfer and evaluation, which are being introduced to educational institutions.

I try to teach students to understand the world, to think, to respect people, to invent new things, to learn, to create a healthy lifestyle. I am for my students I try to ensure that learning is new, interesting, and of course has a developing character.

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